

DYNAMIC BURST STRAIN OF COMPOSITE CYLINDERS - A NOVEL TEST METHOD

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INTRODUCTION

When polymeric composites are used as ablating thermal insulants it is important that they are at least as reliable as the structure they protect, and usually they must strain with that structure. The safe design strain of a thermal insulant must therefore match that of a modern high strength material. Now fibre reinforced moulding compounds are commonly used as insulants, the fibres being sufficiently refractory to stabilise the polymer char. At least in the case of rigid insulants based on phenolic resins, the fibres also provide integrity to the uncharred resin.

Coupon tests show that such materials are very variable locally, often so variable in fact that no safe value of design strain can be found from such tests. However, it was found that the critical defect size for the asbestos-phenolic compositions used was normally large (greater than ten millimetres) and therefore a large test specimen was needed, preferably a tubular one. This was a characteristic component shape and would therefore also reflect material variations due to moulding conditions.

To provide adequate design data on both mean and statistical variation it was required to make many tests, covering a wide range of representative conditions, the extreme being a straining time of two milliseconds at a temperature of -40°C . This paper describes the development of a suitable test and its application to some orthodox rigid insulants and to compositions which are nominally more flexible.

Fig 1 - Tubular test piece burst on matching steel taper

Fig 2 - Dimensions of test piece

Principle

The configuration adopted is shown in Fig 1. The composite tubes were moulded with a small but accurate and uniform taper running the length of the bore, down which an identical, fitting steel taper could be driven to burst each tube in hoop tension. In this way, the axial movement of the incompressible taper produced a proportional strain in the tube. Fig 2 illustrates the specimen used. The taper had therefore to travel almost the length of the tube to produce a mean strain of 3% in the bore, and the taper had then to be more than twice the tube length. The development of the test was then divided into two parts. The first verified the technique at orthodox strain rates by driving the lubricated taper with the compression cage of a Hounsfield Tensometer. Load and displacement were then measured for comparison with coupon tests on the same material.

The second part required more instrumentation. A massive dropweight was used to drive the calibrated taper (Fig 3) without significant loss of velocity after first contact. The initial position of the taper before impact had first been photographed. A conducting spiral painted on each tube enabled the first crack to be detected when continuity was lost. This impulse operated a high speed flash to photograph the immediate position of the taper and frequently that of the crack too. The strain to break was then calculated as before from the observed movement of the taper.

Burst Strain at Orthodox Rates

The surface of the steel taper was sprayed very lightly with PTFE aerosol, it was fitted into the specimen and driven forward in the testing machine to measure load and displacement at a constant rate of travel. The starting point was determined accurately by extrapolating the load-displacement plot back to zero. A specimen could fail in wholly brittle fashion (Type B) or could produce a stable crack (Type A failure) identified by a sharp drop in applied load, depending on elastic energy available in the strained specimen. In either case, the first through-thickness crack was taken as a failure in the function of the insulant.

The calculation of bursting strain was made from the imposed strain existing in the bore, halfway down the length of the specimen. This gives an uncertainty of $\pm 2\%$ for the extremes of the bore. For the purposes of calculation, fracture was thus assumed always to start within the bore material, the hoop strain in the external surface being lower. It is difficult to prove this assumption, but the data were to be applied to components of similar shape and so the error introduced by it was small. Weibull statistics may of course be used to estimate the effect of such changes in size and shape.

Comparison with Coupon Tests

Table 1 lists the strains for first cracking in tubular specimens made of a commercial asbestos-phenolic moulding flock. No significant trends were detected by varying the rate of loading over an order of magnitude within one batch, but there was a difference between the two batches of twenty specimens each, with mean values of $0.82\% \pm 0.17$ and $0.92\% \pm 0.15$, which is probably significant.

The coupon test method of measuring strength in two directions at right angles in a compression moulded panel had given $0.72\% \pm 0.22$ and $0.83\% \pm 0.16$ for strains to failure of this material. The tube bursting test therefore appears to measure slightly higher strain values in this variable material,

and with greater certainty. We believe this is because regions of low strain to break which would grossly weaken a coupon specimen are tolerated in the larger tubular specimen. (Weibull statistics blindly applied to too small a specimen would of course predict the opposite.)

TABLE 1 % STRAIN RESULTS FOR COMMERCIAL ASBESTOS-PHENOLIC MOULDINGS
(a) Static Burst Tests

Batch Ref	5041004			4051701			
	1D	2D	1D+2D	3D	4D	5D	3D+4D+5D
Group Ref							
Crosshead Speed mm/min	6.35	6.35	6.35	6.35	50	100	
Individual results Suffix A or B refers to type of failure - A-falling load stable cracking B-immediate fracture	0.88 B 1.01 B 0.80 A 0.66 A 0.99 A 1.14 B 0.89 B 0.69 A 0.59 A 0.72 A 1.00 B 0.91 B	0.78 A 0.75 A 0.49 A 0.85 A 1.00 B 0.80 B 0.99 B 0.64 A 0.54 A	As for 1D and 2D	1.05 B 1.10 A 0.75 A 0.79 B 0.99 B 0.74 A 1.03 B 0.57 B 0.84 B 1.04 B	0.99 A 1.00 B 1.07 B 0.88 B 0.82 A	1.11 B 1.02 B 0.98 A 0.93 A 0.73 A	As for 3D 4D 5D
Mean X	0.76	0.86	0.82	0.89	0.95	0.89	0.92
Standard Deviation σ	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.20	0.10	0.16	0.15
X - 3 σ			0.30				0.47
C of V %			21.6				16.0

(b) Comparable Results for Coupon Specimens from Compression-moulded panels

'A' Direction		C V %	'B' Direction		C V %
Mean Strain %	X - 3 σ		Mean Strain %	X - 3 σ	
0.72 \pm 0.22	0.06	30.6	0.83 \pm 0.16	0.35	19.0

The effect of reduced variability in the burst test is best demonstrated from measurements on experimental rubber-modified asbestos-phenolics in which the mean strain to break has been successfully increased to 3% in one case and to 4.5% in the other (Table 2). The coefficients of variation observed in the burst tests are expected levels for moulding compounds. On the other hand, those for coupon tests show so much scatter from one direction to another and within each direction, that it is impossible to derive any acceptable design figure.

TABLE 2 % STRAIN RESULTS FROM RUBBER MODIFIED ASBESTOS/PHENOLIC MIXES

(a) Static Burst Test

Material Reference	EPM 194	EPM 195
Individual Results (All Type B failure mode)	3.21	3.86
	3.14	3.26
	2.92	5.09
	3.28	4.25
	3.11	5.67
	3.24	3.76
	3.36	4.20
	2.56	4.28
	3.15	4.24
	3.28	3.68
	3.29	4.80
	3.56	5.12
	2.84	5.96
	2.31	
Mean X	3.08	4.55
Standard Deviation σ	0.32	0.82
X - 3σ	2.12	2.09
C of V %	10.5	18.1

(b) Comparable Results for Coupon Specimens

Material	'A' Direction		C V %	'B' Direction		C V %
	Mean Strain %	X- 3σ		Mean Strain %	X- 3σ	
EPM 194	2.10	Neg	49.6	1.63	Neg	35.3
EPM 195	5.2	Neg	37.6	5.7	Neg	34.7

Fig 4 - Crack propagation during dynamic burst

Fig 3 - Sketch of dynamic burst test at moment of impact

Dynamic Burst Tests

Each tube was masked and painted with a conducting spiral track, the complete 8 mm width of which had to be severed before the presence of a crack was recognised electrically. For this reason the pitch of the spiral was originally kept small in relation to the width of the track, to minimise uncertainty of crack length. The flash unit used in the final version of the apparatus introduced a total delay of seven microseconds (relative to the total strain time of 2-4 milliseconds) during which a crack could grow by some 50 mm, apparently approaching the velocity of sound of the tube material (Fig 4). Reliable contacts with the conducting spiral were held with toroidal springs slipped over each end of the tube. These proved insensitive to the shock of impact.

The tubes were moulded with a flange at the base and the flange was located with a clearance of about 1 mm in a heavy steel support plate (Fig 3) allowing the tube to dilate and giving the hardened steel taper free access through it. Supporting pads of timber and rubber were added to collect the dropweight and to prevent crushing of the cracked specimen. The initial position of the taper was photographed after it had been seated by imposing a small, measured dilation of the tube diameter, about 0.05%, from which the true start position was calculated.

The dropweight of 20 Kg was hauled to a height of 2.5 metres and mounted on an electric bomb release. A plastic guide tube had been fitted to ensure that the falling weight struck the taper squarely. The kinetic energy of the weight at impact was 490 joules, which vastly exceeds the work of fracture to cleave the specimen and the elastic energy stored prior to this. It was therefore safe to assume that the strike velocity would be maintained during the test, ie a strain rate of 250% per second, which is more than three orders faster than was attained in the static tests. The camera shutter was electrically operated by the dropweight as it passed a proximity switch. It was normally opened for about 0.5 seconds, so the specimen and background were therefore shielded from stray light.

A set of results was taken on the material of the second batch of Table 1. These are shown in Table 3 and show a lower mean and higher standard deviation. However, one of the results was an exceptionally low value (0.23%) and it is this reading alone which increases the standard deviation. Either in this one result we have witnessed a very unlikely event, or more probably, the distribution of breaking strain shows a small secondary peak. The fracture faces of this tube were smooth, unlike the ragged hairy fractures observed on other specimens. Thus the measurement itself appears genuine and was associated with a long flow line in the original moulding compound. It was therefore concluded that the dynamic test could be conducted with the same precision as the static test, which was also confirmed later with more consistent experimental materials, where the material variability had been reduced to $\pm 10\%$.

Over the four orders of strain rate it is also much more likely than not that the burst strain has declined by 10% in a rigid asbestos-phenolic compound.

Fig 5 - High velocity crack in rubber-modified asbestos-phenolic tested at low temperature

Fig 6 - Increase in dynamic modulus of the rubber-modified phenolic below freezing point

TABLE 3 DYNAMIC BURST TESTS ON COMMERCIAL ASBESTOS-PHENOLIC

Batch Ref: 4051701
Strain Rate: 250% sec⁻¹

Individual Burst Strains (descending order)	Mean and SD	Restricted Mean and SD (see text)
1.07 0.93 0.87 0.86 0.81 0.80 0.76 0.74 0.72 0.70 0.50 0.23	0.75 ± 0.21	0.80 ± 0.15

Measurements at Low Temperature

The dynamic burst technique is particularly useful for measurements at low temperatures, because simpler apparatus is required. The expansion mismatch of tube materials and steel taper was sufficiently small that they could be assembled and conditioned in a cooling bath, then transferred to the drop test and burst immediately. For intermediate temperatures, a measured time lapse-temperature rise curve was used. As an example of the value of the method, Table 4 (a) shows a set of results obtained in this way on the rubber-modified phenolic asbestos material which had attained 3% average strain to break in the static test at room temperature. The combined affects of strain rate and temperature produce brittle, glassy failures at low strains in the polymer, about 0.77% at -10°C and 0.55% at -40°C (Fig 5). An independent test to measure the change in dynamic stiffness of this moulding compound from its change of resonant frequency as a cantilever, showed that the main transition took place within a few degrees of 0°C (Fig 6). This is a common service temperature, and therefore there was little point in adopting this material, except perhaps as a model. A consistent material which is already rigid, such as BAJ M491 of Table 4 (b), should be a more reliable choice, other things being equal.

TABLE 4 (a) DYNAMIC BURST STRAINS OF RUBBER-MODIFIED PHENOLICS
AT LOW SERVICE TEMPERATURES

Tube No	650	651	660	661	662	667	669	671	666	670	665
Test Temp °C	-40	-40	-40	-40	-10	-10	-10	-10	-5	0	+2
% Strain to crack	0.60	0.64	0.57	0.41	0.78	0.79	0.68	0.83	0.32	0.69	1.1

TABLE 4 (b) EXPERIMENTAL RIGID ASBESTOS-PHENOLIC AT -10°C

Tube No	633	635	636	638	639
Burst strain %	0.72	0.77	0.60	0.69	0.61
Mean = 0.68%					

Checks of Validity of the Dynamic Test

Since the strain is applied within a few milliseconds and it is not possible to view the dynamic process, as much assurance as possible is needed that the test is a valid one. We note the following:

- 1 When the taper is driven slowly into a specimen, the radial dilation is indeed proportional to the axial displacement.
- 2 If a stress-coat varnish is applied on the specimen surface, the crack pattern photographed during and after dynamic bursting is a uniform one. The ultimate cracks on normal test specimens originate randomly over the surface, with little bias to either end.
- 3 The silver paint film used could in itself be stretched 20% before failure, but adhered well to a phenolic surface so that there was no tendency for bridging to occur once a crack began to open.
- 4 Although the majority of each test specimen was obscured from detailed view by the supporting pads, a crack was photographed in one out of every three tests, which was the expected frequency, allowing for the resolution of the film, which could not reveal very oblique crack openings. Test results in which cracks were photographed were compared with those in which they were not. Both groups were distributed evenly about the mean breaking strain, with no bias, showing it was very likely indeed that cracks had always occurred, where they were only indicated electrically and not photographically.
- 5 Where very rigid filled polymers are used, there will be significant elastic compression of the steel taper, reducing the imposed strain, i.e. a maximum correction of some 2%.

Conclusions

- 1 Tubular test specimens are preferred where they represent both the component shape and moulding conditions, and are of sufficient size to allow defects to become critical. A sliding conical taper can be used to impose reproducibly a controlled bursting strain, and its displacement is proportional to that strain. Measurements made in this way are more consistent than coupon tests and more appropriate for design.
- 2 To simulate service conditions, consistent dynamic burst strains have been obtained at strain rates of 250% per second, by driving the taper with a drop-weight and photographing its position as the tube cracks. The simplicity of this method and its visual record of cracks makes it attractive compared with say, hydraulic bursting with multiple strain gauges. It is particularly easy to use for burst measurements at low temperatures, and has revealed serious embrittlement of nominally flexible compositions.
- 3 The test as it stands could be increased in strain rate by about one more order of magnitude, given a suitable driver for the taper. The natural variability of the materials tested masks any direct proof of the numerical accuracy of the method, which is believed to be $\pm 4\%$ from analysis of errors. Tubes of thinner wall could also be introduced to produce a more uniform state of strain through the wall thickness, where this is appropriate.